

BRIDGING THE GAP: EVALUATING ICT COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEE) students at Benguet State University Buguias Campus, identifying challenges they face and proposing necessary enhancements to their training. Utilizing a quantitative research methodology, data were collected through a structured questionnaire assessing students' competencies in hardware, software, and overall ICT literacy. Findings indicate that BEE students generally possess a high level of competence in managing files and using software applications, while their skills in identifying secure websites and managing video conferences are only moderate. Challenges identified include inadequate bandwidth, financial constraints for ICT resources, and insufficient access to data, which hinder effective ICT use in academic settings. Students expressed strong agreement on the importance of integrating technology into lesson plans and the necessity for personalized feedback and dynamic presentation tools. The results underscore the critical need for improved ICT training and resources to enhance the academic performance of future educators. Recommendations include curriculum modifications to better incorporate ICT training, filtering internet access to minimize distractions, and fostering a more robust information literacy framework. The study adheres to ethical standards, ensuring participant confidentiality and informed consent. Overall, this research aims to equip BEE students with essential ICT skills, thereby supporting their professional development in a rapidly evolving educational view.

Keywords: *ICT Literacy, BEE Students, Academic Performance, Curriculum Enhancement*

INTRODUCTION

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has profoundly transformed education, necessitating that aspiring teachers receive adequate ICT training to create engaging and effective learning environments (Adedoyin & Soyibo, 2022). This research aims to evaluate the ICT skills of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students and identify areas where additional support is needed to align their proficiency with educational demands.

Globally, the significance of ICT in education is increasingly recognized, particularly in the Philippines, where the government actively promotes its integration through initiatives like the Department of Information and Communication Technology Act of 2015 (Republic Act No. 10844). The Department of Education (DepEd) further emphasizes this commitment through policies that advocate for the use of technology to enhance teaching and learning processes, aligning with the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (DepEd, 2013). The role of ICT extends beyond mere access to technology; it involves developing competencies that foster effective teaching and learning (Hu et al., 2018).

Despite the potential benefits of ICT, research highlights a gap between the anticipated and actual ICT competencies among future elementary teachers. Factors contributing to this discrepancy include insufficient exposure to essential ICT tools and inadequate training in integrating technology into lesson planning (Clark, 2015). This gap can hinder students' ability to utilize ICT effectively, potentially affecting their academic performance and teaching effectiveness (Lau, 2017).

Previous studies indicate that ICT can enhance educational experiences by facilitating interactive learning environments and providing access to diverse resources (Mathivanan et al., 2021; Voogt et al., 2021). However, challenges such as limited access to technology, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient teacher training persist (Ahmad et al., 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the need for effective ICT integration in educational practices, underscoring the urgency of assessing students' ICT competencies to ensure a successful transition to digital learning environments (CHED CMO No. 4, s. 2020).

Ultimately, this study seeks to equip BEEd students with the necessary ICT skills to navigate modern educational landscapes successfully. By understanding the challenges they face in acquiring ICT competencies, educators can develop targeted strategies to enhance teacher preparation programs, thereby improving the overall quality of education and addressing the evolving demands of the digital age (Inyang, 2017; Catalano, 2019).

Research Questions

The research seeks to examine the challenges and effects of assessing the ICT competence of BEEd students on their academic performance. Despite recognizing the benefits of ICT, the specific challenges and effects of BEEd student's ICT competence on their academic performance remain unexplored. This study aims to address the following key problems:

1. What is the level of knowledge of BEEd students in terms of hardware, software, and ICT literacy?
2. What are the challenges do first-year, second-year, and third-year BEEd students encounter that affect their academic performance?
3. What ICT training or curriculum enhancements can be developed to improve the teaching demonstration sessions and academic performance of BEEd students?

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research methodology to collect and analyze data from respondents, focusing on numerical data to explore the challenges and impacts on the academic performance of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students at Benguet State University Buguias Campus. As noted by Haegele and Hodge (2015), quantitative methods utilize statistical tools to derive insights from surveys and questionnaires. The researchers will specifically design a questionnaire to address the assessment of ICT competence among BEEd students.

The research is localized at Benguet State University Buguias Campus, targeting BEEd students in their first, second, and third years. A total of 52 respondents are included in the study, with 18 first-year, 11 second-year, and 23 third-year students participating. This demographic is crucial for understanding the varying levels of ICT competence across different stages of their education.

Data collection will utilize an adapted questionnaire to assess BEEd students' understanding of hardware, software, and IT literacy, as well as the challenges they face affecting academic success. Additionally, the questionnaire will explore potential curriculum modifications to enhance ICT training. This approach follows the methodologies outlined by Ogun Lana et al. (2018), with data analyzed using established statistical techniques.

Upon retrieving the completed questionnaires, the data will be checked and tallied for accuracy. Descriptive statistical analysis will classify and analyze the data, employing a rating scale to evaluate students' knowledge of ICT and the challenges they encounter. This includes categorizing responses into levels of knowledge and agreement regarding proposed training and curriculum enhancements, thus providing a comprehensive overview of the students' ICT competencies and educational needs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings from the study on the ICT literacy levels of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students, the challenges they face, and the proposed enhancements to their training. The analysis reveals significant variations in knowledge across hardware, software, and overall ICT literacy, indicating that BEEd students possess varying degrees of competence in these areas. Previous research, such as that by Hu et al. (2018), emphasizes the importance of ICT integration in education, highlighting how it can enhance learning experiences and outcomes.

The knowledge levels of BEEd students regarding ICT indicate a generally high level of competence overall. The highest-rated capability was managing files across different storage systems, while the ability to identify secure websites was rated lowest. This aligns with findings from Nwosu et al. (2020), which noted that information literacy skills are crucial for academic success in a digital environment. The statistical significance of these findings underscores that students are generally knowledgeable about ICT functions, which facilitate effective communication and enhance educational access.

Several challenges were identified that impede BEEd students' ability to leverage ICT effectively. These include low bandwidth, lack of funds for ICT gadgets, and insufficient access to data for browsing. These findings corroborate earlier studies, such as those by Ahmad et al. (2019), which pointed to infrastructural and financial constraints affecting students' engagement with technology. Such barriers significantly hinder the effective use of ICT in their studies, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address these challenges.

In terms of necessary ICT training and curriculum enhancements aimed at improving academic performance, students expressed strong agreement on several proposed strategies. Key areas include the effective integration of technology into lesson plans and utilizing technology for personalized feedback. This reflects insights from Furlong and Davies (2021), who argued that effective ICT training is essential for fostering inclusive and engaging educational environments. The consensus among students on the importance of targeted ICT training highlights the need for educational stakeholders to support ongoing professional development in an increasingly digital learning landscape.

Hence, the study underscores the critical role of ICT in the educational development of BEEd students at Benguet State University Buguias Campus. The results indicate a pressing need for enhanced training and resources to overcome existing challenges, ensuring that these future educators are well-equipped to utilize technology effectively in their classrooms. By addressing the gaps identified, educational stakeholders can foster the ongoing professional development of pre-service teachers, facilitating a more effective integration of ICT in their teaching practices. This approach is crucial for preparing educators to navigate and thrive in the complexities of modern educational environments.

Conclusions

The study reveals that BEEd students demonstrate a high level of knowledge in managing, copying, and moving files, as well as in creating and editing digital text files and using advanced search engine features. However, their competence in managing video conferences and identifying secure websites is only moderate. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (Ha1) was accepted.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that BEEd students largely agree on the challenges affecting their academic performance, with significant concerns about slow network bandwidth and insufficient funds for ICT devices. They also express agreement regarding the lack of financial resources for data subscriptions, network restrictions, and inadequate information literacy training at the university. The statistical results underscore the significance of these challenges.

Additionally, the students strongly agree on the importance of integrating technology into lesson plans, providing personalized feedback, supporting blended learning environments, and utilizing interactive tools for dynamic presentations and assessments. The statistical analysis confirms the high significance of these agreements concerning the need for ICT training and curriculum enhancements for BEEd students.

Recommendations

Facilitators and learners should continue to utilize ICT to support learning across all subjects. To enhance students' proficiency with computers, the BSU curriculum must be thoughtfully designed. Additionally, the university administration should implement filtered websites to minimize the misuse of internet resources, such as online games, which can waste data. The curriculum should also incorporate information literacy components to help students effectively apply their ICT skills, thereby improving their performance and academic achievement. Furthermore, instructors may consider assigning academic requirements and performance tasks that are relevant to ICT to reinforce these skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards to ensure the integrity and welfare of all participants involved. Prior to data collection, researchers obtained informed consent from all Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students participating in the study. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks, and they had the option to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the research process. Personal identifiers were removed from data collection instruments, and all responses were anonymized to protect participant privacy. Data were securely stored and only accessible to the research team to ensure confidentiality.

Additionally, the researchers were transparent about the use of data and its potential impact on academic programs. Findings will be shared with relevant stakeholders to contribute to the ongoing improvement of ICT integration in the BEEd curriculum while safeguarding participant anonymity.

Ethical approval was sought and granted from the appropriate institutional review board, ensuring that the study complied with established ethical guidelines in educational research. By following these ethical standards, the study aimed to foster a respectful and responsible research environment.

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